

**MOVAROUNNAHR CHIGATOY NATION POLITICAL
COMPOSITION HISTORY**

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Abstract: in this article, there has always been a great interest in the study of empires that existed in world history. In particular, the path taken by the tribes-tribe associations, which did not have a unified state system, but founded a large kingdom by increasing their military power, as a special "phenomenon", has been the focus of researchers' attention. In this regard, one can give an example of the desire to research the political, socio-economic and ethno-cultural processes that took place during the military campaigns of Genghis Khan, the founder of the Mongol state, which occupied a large part of the Eurasian continent, and the reign of his successors.

Key words: world history, tribe and clan, years of independence in Uzbekistan, history, Chigatoi tribe, Central Asia, Movarounnahr, Mongol era.

According to the sources of the Middle Ages, at the end of the 12th century and the beginning of the 13th century, processes of unification of Mongolian tribes and peoples into a powerful state took place. In written sources, Mongols are mentioned for the first time under the name menu (menva) in the annals of the Chinese Tang Dynasty (618-908). In most sources, the processes of unification of the Mongols are associated with the name of Temuchin. According to information, Temuchin was born in 1155 and was the son of a rich Mongol nobleman, Esugay Bahadur.

By the middle of the 12th century, most of the Turkic and Tungus-Manchu tribes living around Lake Baikal, in the territory of present-day Mongolia, began to be influenced by Esugai Bahadir. After Egusay was killed in 1185 during the wars against the Tatar and Markite tribes, the initiative passed to his son Temuchin. During the years 1186-1204, Temuchin united not only the Mongols, but also many neighboring tribes, such as the Tatars, Markites, Karaites, Jaloyirs, Naimans, Uighurs, and Garluqs, under his power, and founded a powerful state.

In the spring of 1206, Temuchin, who had fully established his power on the banks of one of the tributaries of the Onon River in Mongolia, called a general congress of the Mongols. At this congress, where Temuchin's supporters - Mongol nobles gathered - he was solemnly declared the supreme Mongol ruler - *kh*an, and the chief shaman of the state, Teb Tangriy, gave him the honorary title of "Chingiz Khan" ("Chingiz Khan" means strong, great).

At the congress, Genghis Khan raised his flag, introduced ten positions and presented it to his relatives. The city of Karakorum in the desert will be the capital of the new state. The new Mongol state was called Eke Mungol ulus (Great Mongol state) and its management was transferred to the hands of "Altan urug" (Golden clan).

Having strengthened his position and power, Genghis Khan reformed his military forces and began to expand the borders of his state. He subjugated the Tanguts in 1209, the Uighurs in 1211, and northern China together with the capital city of Zhongdu (Beijing) in 1215. Thus, by the end of the tenth decade of the 13th century, there were two large states in the East - Khorezmshah - Anushtegins and Genghis Khan, and war between them was inevitable. For example, during the Dashti Kipchak campaign in 1215, Khorezmshah faced the Mongol army led by Joji (now in the deserts of Torgay region of Kazakhstan). The Mongols, who had won over their enemies, the Markites, who had retreated to the west, fought for a day with Khorezmshah's 60,000-strong army. Joji Khan, who did not receive any

instructions from Genghis Khan about this battle, was forced to retreat the next day.

Between 1215 and 1218, ambassadors were exchanged several times between Khorezmshah and Genghis Khan. According to Rashiddin, Genghis Khan informed Khorazmshah in 1218 that he "sees him among his sons". Sultan Muhammad was well aware that the East represents this dependence in diplomacy. In addition, about 100 merchants in the group of 450 ambassadors sent to Khorezm by Genghis Khan in 1218 were assigned the task of espionage. Therefore, this caravan was looted in the city of O'tror, and the ambassadors were killed.

After this incident, both sides began to prepare for war. According to An-Nasawi, he did not take into account a number of proposals made by Sultan Muhammad in a meeting called in Urganch in connection with the battle with Genghis Khan. For example, he did not follow the advice of his eldest son Jalaluddin, the governor of Khojand, Temur Malik, to gather all the military forces (according to A. Zia, the number of troops was around 600 thousand people - E.B.) to the main points or to attack the enemy and divided the troops into large cities.

In 1219, Genghis Khan began marching on the state of the Khorezmshahs with about 200,000 main military forces led by his sons. These forces spent the summer on the banks of the Irtish River that year and crossed the border in September. Having crossed the border, Genghis Khan and his army gathered near the city of Otror in the southern Kazakh deserts near the Syrdarya and divided it into four parts. Together with Chigatoy, Oktoy leaves Otror with a part of the army to besiege it. The second part, under the leadership of Dzhojji, will be sent to conquer the cities of Jand, Yangikent, Borchiligkent, Sighnoq on the upper reaches of the Syrdarya. The third part, headed by Uloq Nuyon and Suketu Cherbu, will be assigned to occupy Khojand and Banokat south of Otror. The main fourth part, headed by Genghis Khan himself, went to occupy the big cities - Samarkand and Bukhara.

As a result of these campaigns, the cities of Otror, Jand, Yangikent, Borchiligkent in 1219, Khojand, Bukhara, Samarkand in 1220, Termiz and Urganch in 1221 were conquered by the Mongols. According to the sources, cities such as Urganch, named "Capital of the Sultans of the World" and "Cradle of Great Children of Humanity", Bukhara, named "Qubbatul Islam", and Samarkand, named "Saiqali Royi Zamin", were looted. Some cities, such as Ortor, Sighnoq, Borchiligkent, became deserts for a long time. The Arab historian ibn al-Asirjughul (1160-1244), who lived in this period, described the horrors of the Mongol invasion as follows: "They (the Mongols) did not show mercy to anyone, on the contrary, they killed wives, children, men, they cut open the bellies of pregnant women and killed unborn babies. ... The waves of this calamity spread in different directions, and its tragedy became general, and it spread over all the provinces as the wind drives the clouds in different directions.

A people came out from the borders of China and destroyed, slaughtered and plundered the provinces of Kashgar and Balasagun in Turkestan. The Tatars did not leave any cities alive, they destroyed all the land on their way. They set fire to everything they did not like.

Thus, as a result of plundering wars, by the middle of the 20s of the 13th century, Genghis Khan was able to establish his authority in the territories from North China in the East to the Amudarya in the West. In August 1227, Genghis Khan died while marching into Asia, on the Tanguts. As a result of the military campaigns of Genghis Khan, in 1260, one of the largest states of nomads in history was established - a huge empire that included the territories from the Amur to the Yellow Sea in the East and from the Danube to the Euphrates in the West.

"Yasok"s. Khan's power and state administration. As early as 1203, a set of laws, which did not yet have a system, was created in the Mongol state, which included labels (commands), yasak (laws), and bilik (advices). "Great Yasog" or Genghis Khan's Yasog (Mongol - zasok, yosun) means "rule", "law". The Yasog

was adopted in its entirety at the 1206 Mongol nobles' congress, revised in 1218, and revised for the last time in 1225. According to Juvaini, weapons were written in Uyghur script on amulets (folded papers) and called "Great Book of Weapons" ("Yasanomai buzurg"). These scrolls were kept by princes who were relatively prestigious. The original version of the weapons has not reached us. Some of its parts are abbreviated in the works of Juvaini, Rashididdin, Wassaf, Ibn Batuta, Abul Faraj, and Makrizi.

"Yasok" laws were drawn up in a sharp and very strict tone based on the ancient customs and traditions of the Mongols and the essence of the existing political system, reflecting the patriarchal system.

From the information of medieval history researchers, it can be concluded that the main purpose of Genghis Khan's laws was to establish a new system of law that meets the requirements of the feudal state. Observance of prohibitions was the obligation not only of every citizen in the state, but also of the khans.

It should be noted that the Yasoks mainly expressed a nomadic lifestyle. Many territories conquered by the Mongols, especially the people of Central Asia, which had their own legal traditions from ancient times, were extremely difficult to submit to the new laws. Because peoples who lived a sedentary cultural life for centuries could not accept the traditions of nomads. Many aspects of socio-economic and cultural life were not reflected in Yasogs, and some rules denied Muslim religious rights and local population traditions. That is why there were many clashes between Yasoq supporters and local residents.

Although the Mongol invasion did not change the social structure of Central Asia as a whole, in many cases it paved the way for the revival of steppe traditions and brought new directions to the political and economic life of many subjugated peoples. The principle that the empire was the private property of the khan clan prevailed in the state management of the empire established by the Mughals. At the time, Juvaini described this peculiarity of the state administration as follows:

"Although from the outside, the administration and the country are entrusted to one person, in fact, all the relatives on the father's side (males) of that person jointly own the land and the common wealth."

In medieval sources, the authority of the khan in Mughal society is generally given as sheepish: as a mother cares for her child, the khan is obliged to care for his dependents and troops. His dependents and troops consider the ruler as their father. Also, they must obey the ruler sincerely, serve without treachery and agree to sacrifice their lives to support his authority.

According to Mughal tradition, the entire Mughal congress to elect a new ruler was convened by the oldest or interim ruler of the Genghis clan. The time of the convention is fixed in advance and announced to all the ulas by couriers. At the designated time and place, princes and their relatives, princesses, grooms, dignitaries, emirs, officials, as well as rulers subject to the Mughals arrived with their precious gifts and gifts from all the tribes of the vast empire. The convention lasted several weeks (for example, 40 days in 1229, 4 weeks in 1246, etc.)

In the Mughals, the ruling khan was the supreme ruler in the state administration, and according to tradition, the khan's power was a guarantee of common interests, stability and justice in society. Each adult member of the ruler's household, including the ruler's widow, was assigned a certain number of artisans and farming districts from the general territory of the empire. The profit from them was used to meet the needs of the owner's palace and troops.

At the same time, every adult Mughal prince claimed el (certain clans and tribes) and yurt (territorial oasis, land for grazing). In such conditions, they had to live with their clansmen in their winter and summer residences and not interfere in administration and tax collection. The management of settled regions, the collection of taxes from agricultural oases and handicraft workshops and "sending it to the right person" was the responsibility of special persons appointed by the great khan, and then local rulers.

There were many military nobles in the Genghis state, and both Genghis Khan himself and the subsequent Mongol khans rewarded them for their services to the khan and the state. Such recipients were called tarkhan. They were exempt from various taxes, and the spoils obtained during hunting and wars were considered their personal property.

Internecine wars between Chingizis. After the death of Genghis Khan in 1227, his state was divided into the following four uluses:

1. Jozhiylar (Zhozhi generation) – Dashti Kipchak.
2. Chigatai (Chigatai generation) - Ettisuv, Movarounnahr, East Turkestan.
3. Khulaghis (descendants of Khulagu, son of Tulukhan) - Iran.
4. Yuan dynasty (Tulukhan generation) - Mongolia and China.

The historical fate of these four dynasties was different. The descendants of Tulukhan (Yuan Dynasty) who ruled China become Chinese. They ruled China until 1368, and ruled Mongolia until the 17th century. After the death of the last Khulagi ruler, Abu Sa'id, in 1335, the Khulagi state in Iran was in crisis from 1336-1353. The Chigatai dynasty existed until the end of the 17th century. The descendants of Jojikhans existed in Dashti Kipchak and other regions until the middle of the 19th century. During the entire reign, mutual wars between them almost did not stop.

During the process of building a powerful state of Genghis Khan, two opposing trends emerged among the great Mongolian nobles and military. The first of these directions consisted of positive relations with the khan's power, centralization processes of the state, conquered peoples, their economy, culture and religion. Supporters of this direction were Ugedei (1229-1241 AD), the patron of Muslims and organizers of caravan trade, Kebek Khan (1318-1326 AD), who regulated taxes and gave great importance to the processes of city construction and settlement.

Until the end of the 13th century, the reactionary, extremely hostile to the first direction, the second direction was also strong, and they were supported by a large part of the Mongolian military-nomadic nobility. Adhering to Mughal traditions and customs, these nomadic nobles viewed the sedentary lifestyle and the local population with hostility. The conquered peoples did not want to get close to the local nobility, and they looked at the settled population as an object of plunder. They considered cities and forts to be centers of rebellion against the Mughals and destroyed them. They were also enemies of Islam and local cultures.

By the middle of the 13th century, the struggle between these two political forces had subsided. Because all the Mongol nobles took an active part in the ongoing invasion wars and almost did not interfere in the administration of the conquered people. At the end of the 60s of the 13th century, as a result of the division of the single Mongol empire into several Mongol states, the Chigatoi clan was formed, and the political struggle between the Chigatoi nobles began. The first two Chigatai Khans - Mubarak Khan and Barak Khan - tried to approach Movarounnahr. Mubarak Khan moved from Ettasuv to the Angren River oasis with several Mongol tribes (jalayirs, saroyis, barlos, etc.) and was elected khan here in 1266. And Barak Khan had his property in Chaganiyan (Surkhan Oasis).

The policy implemented in Movarounnahr was strongly opposed by the nomadic Mughal nobility. In 1269, Haidu Khan gathered a congress of Mongol princes and nobles in Talas Valley. The decisions taken at this congress had the character of mutual agreement. According to Rashididdin, the participants of the congress agreed among themselves and decided "from now on to live in the mountains and steppes, not to stay around the cities, not to graze cattle on cultivated lands, not to impose unjustified taxes."

For about half a century after Mubarak Khan and Barak Khan, the Chigatai Khans did not try to build their residence in Movarounnahr. Their residence was in Ettisuv. The large influx of nomadic Mongols into Ettisuv, as well as the neglect of

the interests of the local settled population by the Mongolian nomadic nobles led to the transformation of the entire Ettiuv territory into pastures by the end of the 13th century. Also I. V. According to Petrushevshsky, Khulagis and Chigatai Mongols took part in the destruction and arson of Bukhara in 1273.

At the beginning of the 14th century, the khans of Chigatoy again tried to restore all ties with the cultural regions, take control of them, and centralize the state. This policy of the Khans was fully supported by the rural and urban population. However, during the years 1316-1319, Prince Yasovur (son of Khan Yasu Munka), who was a supporter of nomadic lifestyle and other wars, waged destructive wars in Movarounnahr and Khorasan. As a result of the wars conducted by Yasovur, the settled population suffered a lot and was humiliated. Many cultivated fields were destroyed, villages, castles and cities were destroyed. In July 1319, the combined forces of Kebek Khan and the governor of Herat, Malik Ghiyasiddin, defeated the Yasovur forces. Yasovur was killed.

Oloviddin Tarmashirin, who was in power in 1326-1334, strongly defended the traditions of settled life. Dissatisfied with Tarmashirin's policy, nomadic Mongol nobles revolted and killed him in 1334. After Tarmashirin, Changshi (1334), Bozan (1334-1338), Eson Temur (1338-1342), Muhammad (1342-1343), who were in power, saw significant changes in the socio-political and economic life of Movarounnahr. it didn't happen. On the contrary, the power of the local tribes, the influence of the clan chiefs will become stronger by this time, and the power of the rulers of Chigatai will begin to decrease.

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